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Consumer purchase behavior on brand-name products through online channels: A study of consumers in Muang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat Province, Thailand

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Abstract

The objective of this research is to investigate consumer behavior and factors influencing the purchasing of brand-name products through online channels, specifically focusing on consumers in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat Province. The study aims to gain insights into the behaviors and factors influencing consumer purchasing decisions in this specific region. The research will involve collecting data from a sample group of 400 participants.

The statistical analysis will encompass descriptive statistics, such as frequency, mean, and standard deviation, as well as inferential statistics, including the chi-square test, multiple regression analysis, and logistic regression analysis. The study findings reveal the following key insights: Firstly, personal factors, such as gender, occupation, and income, significantly impact the choice of purchasing channels, types of products purchased, preferred payment methods, average expenditure per purchase, and recipients of the purchased products. Secondly, risk factors play a crucial role in determining the preferred purchasing channels and payment methods among consumers. Thirdly, the acceptance of technology significantly influences the choice of payment methods adopted by consumers. Finally, perceived value factors have a significant impact on the choice of purchasing channels, primary motivations for making purchases, and preferred payment methods.

Keyword :Purchasing Behavior; Consumer Behavior; Brand-name products; Online channels

1. Introduction

The development of communication technology has led to the emergence of a globalized world, also known as globalization. In addition to the widespread dissemination of news and information worldwide, globalization has also facilitated the flow of trends, ideas, and technology, significantly influencing people within countries. This has resulted in the adoption of certain behaviors, such as the consumption of branded products from foreign countries, including clothing, bags, perfumes, shoes, watches, and more. These branded products often come with a higher price tag due to the social acceptance and preference they receive in society. They are perceived to possess both quality and a desirable image (Pennipa, P., 2008).

The globalization that is based on the logic of capital expansion and the development of communication systems has facilitated the extensive exchange of news and information through various media channels, such as television and cable TV. Consequently, products from different parts of the world have more opportunities to showcase themselves to consumers in various forms. Furthermore, the low transportation costs in the maritime industry have contributed to increased international trade and the exchange of goods, leading to the diffusion of cultures and trends (Somkiat.e, Arisa Suksom, 2009). The growth of consumer culture has made consumption a more meaningful activity, particularly in terms of symbolic meanings. This includes the consumption for the purpose of distinction, as well as the process of

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imitation. These two aspects influence the perception of young consumers, who believe that consuming such products signifies wealth, happiness, and a sense of freedom (Baudrillard, 1999).

The development of communication technology has given rise to globalization, which has resulted in the widespread exchange of information and the flow of trends and technology worldwide. As a consequence, people's behaviors have been influenced, including the consumption of branded products from foreign countries. These products, such as perfumes and cosmetics, leather bags and belts, and watches and accessories, have a high import value, reaching billions of Baht. The increasing import value can be attributed to advancements in information awareness and communication, which have created popularity and demand for foreign products. These preferences and values are not limited to Bangkok or tourist destinations but are prevalent throughout the country. For instance, in Nakhon Si Thammarat, a province with relatively high average household income ranking third in the southern region, there has been an emergence of offline stores selling branded bags, such as Superb Brandname and Lin Brandname. This reflects the growing popularity and demand for such products within the province.

However, the number of offline stores selling branded products is not significant. Moreover, the development of technology has enabled online channels for purchasing branded products, offering consumers a wide range of options. The online platform has become a popular avenue for buying and selling branded products, providing consumers with direct access to authorized sellers (official). This has led to the researchers' interest in studying the behavior of consumers in purchasing branded products online in the urban area of Nakhon Si Thammarat province.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Online Shopping Behavior

Online shopping behavior refers to the behaviors associated with purchasing products and services online. This includes factors such as frequency of purchases, expenditure, and duration of each purchase. Online shopping is considered a convenient way for consumers to save time as they can make purchases from anywhere at any time (Adil Bashir, 2013). One of the advantages is that consumers can easily compare prices of similar products from different sellers (Reibstein, 2002). Sellers of online products have a primary responsibility to create attractive and user-friendly websites to attract and convert visitors into buyers. Additionally, the readiness of the product acts as a stimulus for buyers, and customer satisfaction is crucial as it impacts long-term relationships between customers and sellers (Harris & Goode, 2010).

2.2. Technology Acceptance

Tella Adeyinka (2014) discussed Davis's (1989) theory of technology acceptance, influenced by two main factors: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness refers to the belief that using technology will result in the highest benefits, directly influencing future usage. Perceived ease of use refers to the perception of how easy it is to use technology, indirectly affecting the intention to use it in the future.

2.3. Risk Acceptance

The risks associated with online shopping can be categorized into three aspects. Firstly, product risk refers to the possibility that the product may not perform as expected. Secondly, financial risk involves the potential loss of money during online payment transactions. Lastly, privacy risk refers to the potential loss of personal information, such as unauthorized disclosure of customer data (Jain & Kulhar, 2019).

2.4. Concepts and Theories related to Brand Equity

Brand equity consists of five components according to Aaker (1991): brand loyalty, brand awareness, perceived quality, brand associations, and other proprietary brand assets. These components contribute to the overall value of a brand.

2.5. The concept and theory related to the decision-making process in purchasing

Engel, Blackwell, and Miniard (1990) mentioned that the 6W and 1H questions are tools for analyzing consumer behavior in order to understand the characteristics of consumer behavior that can be used to develop products and services that meet the needs of the target market, creating satisfaction towards the products and services. These questions consist of the following:

Who: Who is the target group (occupants)?, What: What do we want to sell (object)?, Why: Why do consumers buy?, When: When do consumers make the purchase?, Where: Where can consumers make the purchase?, Whom: Who influences the purchasing decision? And How: How do consumers make the purchase decision?

2.6. The concept and theory related to motivation

Motivation can stimulate desires in consumers. Once consumers have developed a desire, they will take various actions to fulfill or achieve their goals. Motivation consists of three interconnected components: Needs: The basic requirements or desires that drive individuals., Drives: The psychological or physiological tension that arises from unfulfilled needs. And Goals: The objectives individuals aim to achieve.

2.7. The concept and theory related to trust

Luhmann (1979) stated that trust represents the level of confidence one person has in another. Organizations need to establish trust with customers to gain their loyalty. Trust is built through the 5Cs: Communication: Effective communication between the organization and customers., Caring and Giving: Demonstrating care and providing assistance to customers., Commitment: Committing to fulfilling promises and meeting customer expectations., Comfort: Providing convenience and comfort to customers., Conflict Resolution: Resolving conflicts and addressing issues that may arise with customers.

Building trust with customers is essential as it leads to customer comfort and a better resolution of conflicts compared to situations where conflicts need to be resolved.

2.8. Goodwill towards a brand

Brand loyalty is an important marketing objective as it leads to repeat purchases without switching to other brands. Brand loyalty arises from personal satisfaction towards a product or service. It is significant for businesses because customer satisfaction leads to repeat purchases, loyalty, and positive word-of-mouth recommendations. Goodwill towards a brand can be divided into two types: Behavioral Brand Loyalty: Loyalty based on consumer behavior, Attitudinal Brand Loyalty: Loyalty based on consumer attitudes. (Gamble Stone & Woodcock, Angsamalak THAISOM, 2023)

2.9. Meaning of Brand Name Products

Brand name products are products that are created to establish a unique identity through their name, symbol, design, or distinctive features. These products are limited in quantity and often have a limited distribution, making them difficult to acquire. The value of brand name products relies more on the emotions they evoke rather than their physical attributes. Brand name products are flexible in terms of pricing and can vary based on individuals' income levels. They are highly sought after and not widely available.

The value of brand name products depends on the reputation and fame of the designer involved in their creation. These products are manufactured using high-quality materials and are recognized for their superior quality. The exclusivity of brand name products cannot be easily found in the general market. As a result, brand name products are highly regarded and accepted on a global scale. (Tarikah Chatkamon, 2023)

3. Material and method

This research is a quantitative study conducted using an online questionnaire (Google Form) as a data collection tool. Convenience sampling technique was used to select the sample. The questionnaire is divided into 6 sections, including screening of the sample group, personal factors, risk factors in online purchasing, technology acceptance, perception of product value, and online brand purchasing behavior. The population used in this study consists of residents in Muang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat Province, with a sample size of 400 individuals determined using Roscoe's formula (1969). The actual sample size is 384 individuals, but an additional 16 individuals were included to account for potential errors. The statistical analysis used includes descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, and standard deviation, as well as inferential statistics such as Chi-square test, multiple regression analysis, and logistic regression analysis.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis is a statistical method used to examine and establish the relationship between two or more independent variables and a dependent variable (Chatsiri Piyaphimolsit, 2005). The purpose is to understand the changes in the dependent variable caused by the influence of the independent variables. This can be observed through the regression coefficients of the independent variables in each equation. There are certain assumptions regarding the variables used in the analysis:

- The independent variables (X) and the dependent variable (Y) should have a relationship.
- The variables should not exhibit multicollinearity, meaning they should not have a high correlation with each other.
- The relationship between the independent variables (X) and the dependent variable (Y) should be linear.
- The distribution of the population should be normal or approximately normal.
- The variance of the errors (e) should be constant across all observed values.

The relationship can be expressed in the form of an equation:

$$\text{Equation in the form of an example } y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots + b_kx_k + e$$

$$\text{Predictive Equation (Forecasting Equation) } \hat{y} = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots + b_kx_k + e$$

Where:

x_i represents the value of each independent variable (using x_i for observed values from the sample and using y hat for estimated or predicted values).

Y represents the value of the dependent variable (using y for observed values from the sample and using y hat for estimated or predicted values).

k represents the number of independent variables in the equation.

b_0 represents the constant term (intercept) of the regression equation (using b_0 for observed values from the sample and using y hat for estimated or predicted values).

b_i represents the regression coefficients of each independent variable x_i (using b_i for observed values from the sample and using y hat for estimated or predicted values). The value of b_i indicates the rate of change of the dependent variable (Y) for a one-unit change in x_i .

e represents the error term or residual between the observed value Y and the predicted value y hat (using e for observed values from the sample) (Pongsak Simmonds, 2017).

Logistic Regression Analysis is a predictive analysis aimed at predicting the likelihood of an event of interest occurring. It utilizes logistic equations created from a set of predictor variables that have data at the interval level or higher. The predictor variables should exhibit a low correlation among themselves, and the analysis should involve a minimum of 30 predictor variables. The main difference between logistic regression analysis and general regression analysis is that the dependent variable (Y) in logistic regression is categorical, whereas in general regression analysis, the dependent variable (Y) is quantitative (Yuth Kaiyawan, 2012).

3.1. Preliminary assumptions for logistic regression analysis are as follows:

- Independent variables should be at least at the interval scale level of measurement. In the case of categorical data, they should be transformed into dummy variables. For binary logistic regression, two values (0 and 1) are assigned, while for multinomial logistic regression, the number of groups in the dependent variable determines the assignments.
- The mean of the error term should be zero and should not be correlated. In other words, $E(e) = 0$.
- There should be no multicollinearity among the independent variables. This means that the independent variables should not have a high correlation among themselves, as it can lead to problems in selecting the significant variables for the dependent variable. Including all independent variables in the model may result in redundancy and unnecessarily large models.
- Logistic regression analysis requires a larger sample size (n) compared to linear regression analysis. A guideline often used is $n \geq 30p$, where p is the number of predictor variables.

The reason for using logistic regression analysis instead of linear regression analysis is that the dependent variable in logistic regression takes on only two values, representing the occurrence or non-occurrence of an event, and the estimated values of the dependent variable (Y hat) are probabilities between 0 and 1. If a linear regression equation were used, the predicted values of Y may fall outside the range of 0 and 1, or have values less than 0 or greater than 1. Logistic regression analysis also assumes that the error term follows a normal distribution, which is not feasible when the dependent variable has only two values (0 and 1) since the error term would only have two possible values. Therefore, the assumption of normally distributed errors and constant error variance cannot be met in logistic regression (Chammaree Chubuathong and Somsri Banditvilai, 2017).

4. Result

4.1. Sample Group

The sample group consisted of 270 individuals, with females comprising 67.2% (n=270) of the group. The majority of respondents were between 20-40 years old, accounting for 66.7% (n=268) of the sample. Almost all respondents had completed a bachelor's degree, accounting for 99.8% (n=401) of the group. In terms of marital status, 73.9% (n=297) of the respondents were married. The majority of the sample worked in private companies, with 77.6% (n=312) being employed in this sector. Additionally, 65.2% (n=262) of the respondents had an average monthly income between 30,001-45,000 Baht.

4.2. Risk Acceptance

Regarding risk acceptance, the respondents agreed with the following risk factors: the risk associated with products was moderately accepted (mean = 3.82), consumers strongly agreed with this risk (mean = 4.83), financial risk was moderately accepted (mean = 3.80), respondents agreed that retailers should have secure payment methods (mean = 4.01), and they expressed concerns about requesting refunds from online financial transactions (mean = 4.08). The risk associated with personal data was moderately accepted (mean = 4.13), respondents agreed that retailers should securely collect customer data (mean = 4.17), and they believed that data should not be disclosed without permission (mean = 4.11).

4.3. Technology Acceptance

The respondents moderately accepted technology (mean = 4.25). The sample group agreed that it was easy to find desired products quickly (mean = 4.30), they searched for product information before making decisions (mean = 4.45), and they agreed that online shopping was convenient (mean = 4.16).

4.4. Perceived Value of Products

The respondents moderately agreed with the value of products (mean = 3.80). They had a moderate level of awareness regarding product brands (mean = 4.31) and believed that brand-name products were a means of accumulating wealth. They could remember the distinct characteristics of their favorite brands, and each brand had different personalities. In terms of product quality, respondents agreed that brand-name products had a longer lifespan, higher value, and provided better customer service compared to non-brand stores. They also showed a strong inclination towards purchasing brand-name products first and agreed to subscribe to brand-related information.

4.5. Online Shopping Behavior

The majority of consumers prefer to use centralized e-commerce platforms such as Shopee/Lazada, with 51% (n=205) of respondents. The next popular choices are Facebook with 9.5% (n=38), brand websites with 7.2% (n=29), Instagram with 5.5% (n=22), and Line with 1.7% (n=7).

4.6. Primary Reasons for Online Purchases

The majority of respondents strongly agree that online shopping aligns with their current lifestyle. The primary payment method used for online purchases is credit/debit cards, with 63.2% (n=254) of respondents.

4.7. Frequently Purchased Products

The most frequently purchased products online are bags/shoes, with 28.9% (n=116) of respondents indicating this preference. The majority of consumers (70.4%, n=283) typically spend less than 10,000 Baht per online transaction. On average, consumers make 5-6 online purchases per year, with 33.1% (n=133) of respondents falling into this category.

4.8. Influences on Purchase Decisions

The majority of respondents (91%, n=366) make online purchases for themselves. Friends/close acquaintances have a significant influence on purchase decisions, with 67.9% (n=273) of respondents considering their opinions. Prior to making a purchase, 74.1% (n=298) of respondents conduct product research, and 72.9% (n=293) compare prices. If satisfied with a product/service, 76.9% (n=309) of respondents would recommend it to others.

4.9. Hypothesis Testing

4.9.1. Hypothesis 1: Personal factors are related to the online purchase behavior of consumers for brand-name products through online channels in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat Province

Table 1 Results of the chi-square analysis examining the relationship between personal factors and the online purchase behavior of consumers for brand-name products through online channels in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat Province

	Gender		Age		Marital Status		Occupation		Income	
	Chi-square	Sig.	Chi-square	Sig.	Chi-square	Sig.	Chi-square	Sig.	Chi-square	Sig.
Purchase Channels										
Brand's Website	17.352	0.000	1.066	0.302	0.186	0.666	16.099	0.000	18.865	0.000
Facebook	23.236	0.000	0.783	0.376	1.034	0.309	12.665	0.002	11.127	0.004
Instagram	23.830	0.000	0.584	0.445	1.128	0.288	25.593	0.000	15.067	0.001
Line	34.038	0.000	1.111	0.292	0.415	0.520	39.209	0.000	20.982	0.000
Centralized Applications such as Shopee/Lazada	0.689	0.708	2.714	0.099	0.193	0.660	4.628	0.099	5.243	0.073
Payment Methods										
PromptPay	16.412	0.000	1.093	0.296	0.883	0.349	22.929	0.000	8.669	0.013
Mobile Banking	22.491	0.000	3.529	0.060	6.895	0.009*	30.676	0.000	16.039	0.013
Frequently Purchased Items										
Jewelry	10.319	0.006	0.907	0.341	0.390	0.533	10.762	0.005	17.670	0.000
Perfume/Cosmetics	6.405	0.041	1.230	0.267	1.475	0.225	6.074	0.048	6.260	0.044
Bags/Shoes	10.809	0.004	1.018	0.313	0.530	0.467	4.623	0.099	1.282	0.527
Clothing/Apparel	2.789	0.248*	0.583	0.445	3.220	0.073	5.965	0.051	13.737	0.001
Household Items	18.588	0.000	1.638	0.201	6.471	0.011*	34.458	0.000	20.744	0.000
Average Amount Spent	15.735	0.000	5.000	0.025*	0.763	0.382	17.122	0.000	10.588	0.004

*Statistical significance level 0.05

According to Table 1, the analysis of the relationship between personal factors and online brand-name purchasing behavior of consumers in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat, reveals that gender, occupation, and income are significantly related to all channels of online purchase, except for the online application channel. Age and marital status, on the other hand, show no significant relationship with brand-name online purchasing behavior.

4.9.2. Hypothesis 2 states that risk factors influence the purchasing behavior of brand-name products through online channels among consumers in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat

From Table 2, the analysis of multiple regression indicates that the risk factor related to product quality significantly affects purchasing through centralized application platforms like Shopee/Lazada (p-value = 0.001). However, the risk factors related to financial transactions and personal data do not have a significant impact on purchasing through centralized application platforms like Shopee/Lazada. Furthermore, the analysis of multiple regression shows that the risk factor significantly affects purchasing branded products through online channels for consumers in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat Province. The risk factor related to financial transactions does not have a significant impact on payment through credit/debit cards (p-value = 0.319), but it does have a significant impact on payment through PromptPay (p-value = 0.015) and Mobile Banking (p-value = 0.013).

Table 2 Results of the multiple regression analysis, indicating the impact of risk factors on the online brand-name purchasing behavior of consumers in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat

	Variable	b	t	p-value
Channels of purchasing products				
application platforms such as Shopee/Lazada)Constant(5.575	10.653	0.000
	Product-related risks	-0.254	-3.287	0.001
	Financial risks	-0.078	-0.883	0.378
	Privacy risks	-0.007	-0.080	0.937
Payment methods				
Credit/Debit Cards	Financial risks	0.051	0.998	0.319
PromptPay	Financial risks	-0.247	-2.436	0.015
Mobile Banking	Financial risks	-0.261	-2.508	0.013

4.9.3. Hypothesis 3: The acceptance of technology affects the purchasing behavior of branded products through online channels for consumers in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat Province

From Table 3, the results of the multiple regression analysis indicate that the acceptance of technology has a significant effect on the purchasing behavior of branded products through the Instagram and Line channels, with p-values of 0.020 and 0.000, respectively. Additionally, the factors related to technology acceptance have a significant impact on the payment channels through PromptPay (p-value = 0.015) and Mobile Banking (p-value = 0.013).

Table 3 Results of multiple regression analysis of the correlation between technology acceptance and purchasing behavior of branded products through online channels

Variable	b	t	p-value
Purchase channels			
Brand's Website	-0.321	-1.669	0.096
Facebook	-0.300	-1.638	0.102
Instagram	-0.357	-2.274	0.024*
Line	-0.428	-3.215	0.001*
application platforms such as Shopee/Lazada	-0.116	-0.862	0.389
Payment channels			
Credit/debit cards	0.051	0.998	0.319
PromptPay	-0.247	-2.436	0.015*
Mobile Banking	-0.261	-2.508	0.013*

4.9.4. Hypothesis 4: Perceived value of products influences the purchasing behavior of consumers for brand-name products through online channels in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat

From Table 4, the results of the multiple regression analysis show that perceived value of products significantly influences the purchasing behavior through Facebook, Instagram, and Line channels, with p-values of 0.009, 0.004, and 0.000, respectively. However, factors related to perceived quality of products and brand loyalty have an impact on all channels except for the intermediary app channels like Shopee/Lazada.

Table 4 Results of multiple regression analysis on the influence of perceived value of products on the purchasing behavior of consumers for brand-name products through online channels in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat

Variable	b	t	p-value
Website			
)Constant(7.275	7.686	0.000
Perceived value of products	-0.309	-1.564	0.119
Perceived quality of products	-0.397	-2.347	0.019*
Brand loyalty	-0.527	-3.047	0.002*
Facebook			
)Constant(7.326	8.159	0.000
Perceived value of products	-0.489	-2.611	0.009*
Perceived quality of products	-0.442	-2.750	0.006*
Brand loyalty	-0.340	-2.070	0.040*
Instagram			
)Constant(7.758	10.400	0.000
Perceived value of products	-0.450	-2.891	0.004*
Perceived quality of products	-0.514	-3.849	0.000*
Brand loyalty	-0.470	-3.443	0.001*
Line			
)Constant(7.794	12.774	0.000
Perceived value of products	-0.568	-4.466	0.000*
Perceived quality of products	-0.522	-4.780	0.000*
Brand loyalty	-0.389	-3.484	0.001*
application platforms such as Shopee/Lazada			
)Constant(3.084	4.499	0.000
Perceived value of products	0.066	0.461	0.645
Perceived quality of products	0.105	0.857	0.392
Brand loyalty	0.110	0.877	0.381

5. Discussion

Based on the analysis of the demographic factors, the majority of the sample group consisted of females aged between 20-40 years old. They had a bachelor's degree education, were mostly married, and employed in private companies with an average monthly income of 30,001-45,000 baht.

Regarding the risk analysis, participants generally agreed that online purchases may not always meet the specified quality of the products. They preferred to buy from stores that have clear identity verification. In terms of financial risk, most respondents were confident in making online payments but had concerns about refund processes in case of errors. They also agreed on the importance of secure personal data protection by online stores.

In the analysis of technology acceptance factors, participants believed that technology provides convenience and easy access to information before making a purchase. In terms of perceived value of products, respondents demonstrated

awareness of product branding, agreed on product quality, and showed brand loyalty. The commonly used online platforms for purchasing were Facebook, and the main reason for choosing online shopping was alignment with their current lifestyle.

The majority of participants preferred to pay through credit/debit cards. The most frequently purchased products were bags and shoes, with an average purchase amount of less than 10,000 baht. They made 5-6 purchases per year for themselves, and their decision-making was influenced by friends or close acquaintances. Participants conducted product research and comparisons before making a purchase decision. Additionally, if they liked a product, they would recommend it to others.

Overall, the findings suggest that consumers in the sample group are receptive to online shopping and technology. They are aware of product quality and value and consider factors such as convenience, personal lifestyle, and recommendations from trusted sources in their decision-making process.

From the hypothetical testing, personal factors are related to the online purchase of brand-name products through various channels by consumers in Mueang District, Nakhon Si Thammarat Province. Personal factors such as age, occupation, and income are related to the choice of purchasing products through websites of brands on Facebook, Instagram, and Line. This is consistent with the research conducted by Wanna Wanmud (2015), which studied personal factors that influence online purchasing behavior. It was found that factors such as gender, age, education level, occupation, and monthly income are related to the factors that influence online purchasing decisions.

The factor of risk acceptance is also related to the selection of brand-name products through online channels, both in terms of product features and personal information. This may be because perceiving risk in online shopping is a personal matter. Regardless of the actual risk level of the product and service, if consumers are not aware of it, it will not affect their consumption behavior. Therefore, the perception of risk by consumers affects online purchasing behavior when consumers are aware of the risks involved. This finding aligns with the research by Leelarsamee, A. (2016), which studied the components of e-commerce websites and trust in purchasing decisions of brand-name products through e-commerce websites by consumers in Bangkok. It was found that trust in purchasing products has an impact on the decision to buy brand-name products through e-commerce websites, particularly in terms of the seller's credibility. Overall, consumers had the highest level of agreement with this factor.

Regarding the factor of technology acceptance, it was found that, in general, it is not significantly related to the selection of brand-name products through online channels. When considering specific aspects, the channels for purchasing products through Instagram and Line were found to be influenced by reasons related to ease of product comparison and pricing. Products such as perfumes/cosmetics and payment methods through PromptPay and Mobile Banking were also found to be related to the selection of brand-name products through online channels. This is consistent with the research conducted by Chatchapat Techakasamsuk and Tiwa Park (2022), which studied technology acceptance and digital marketing communication affecting the purchase decisions of online shoes by Generation X consumers in Bangkok. The hypothetical testing found that technology acceptance and perceived risk related to security did not significantly influence the purchase decisions of online shoes by Generation X consumers in Bangkok. This may be due to the familiarity of most consumers with technology usage, which allows them to accept the risk of security that may occur when making purchases through online channels.

Factors related to the perceived value of products, awareness of product quality, and their impact on purchasing products through Facebook, Instagram, Line, and online channels, in alignment with one's current lifestyle. The product categories mentioned are fragrances/cosmetics and household items. Payment methods include PromptPay, mobile banking, and credit/debit cards. The perceived value of products and awareness of product quality influence purchasing products through the brand's website on Facebook, Instagram, and Line. Reasons for purchasing products through online channels include convenience, the ability to browse products, marketing promotions, and alignment with one's current lifestyle. The relationship between fragrance/cosmetic products, payment methods such as PromptPay and mobile banking, and the decision to purchase brand-name products through online channels is consistent with the research by Rachokan, K. (2020) on creating product value through online social media, influencing consumer decision-making in purchasing Blackmores supplements in Bangkok. The study found that consumers attach importance to communication through websites, Facebook, Line, or Instagram of Blackmores supplements, leading to information acquisition about the products.

Recommendation

- Based on the study results indicating that personal factors influence consumer purchasing behavior of brand-name products through online channels, businesses involved in selling brand-name products online should prioritize this aspect. It is important to target the main demographic group of females, as the survey revealed that females have a higher preference for purchasing products through online channels compared to males. Additionally, they tend to prefer purchasing through intermediary applications such as Shopee and Lazada due to the convenience of product selection and evaluation. Moreover, concerns about risks in online shopping, both regarding product quality and personal data, should be addressed. If consumers make purchases through intermediary applications like Shopee or Lazada, these applications allow product returns if the consumer is dissatisfied with the product or if the received product does not match the advertised description. Furthermore, these applications have official distributor systems, such as LazMall on Lazada or Shopee Mall on Shopee, which are official stores or flagship stores authorized to sell products exclusively from the brands. Therefore, purchasing products from these stores provides consumers with confidence that the products are genuine and properly licensed. This is a significant reason why consumers prefer purchasing products through these intermediary applications.
- Based on the study results, respondents expressed significant concerns about risks, particularly regarding privacy-related risks, when purchasing brand-name products through online channels. This is evident in Table 5.1. Consumers also emphasized the importance of product-related risks. Therefore, businesses that sell products through intermediary applications should implement stringent measures to ensure the security of customer data and prevent any unauthorized data breaches. It is crucial for these businesses to clearly demonstrate their commitment to customer data privacy and security. In terms of financial risks, it was found that this factor does influence the choice of payment methods for online purchases, such as PromptPay or mobile banking. However, financial risks do not significantly affect the use of credit cards for payment, as consumers generally trust and accept the technology associated with debit/credit card usage. Therefore, businesses should provide options for payment via debit/credit cards to accommodate consumer preferences and build trust.
- Fragrances/cosmetics are products that businesses should consider selling in their stores because they are reasonably priced, usually not exceeding 10,000 baht. Survey results also indicate that the majority of consumers make purchases in this category that do not exceed 10,000 baht each time. Additionally, these products are consumable and need to be replenished regularly. Furthermore, factors related to brand loyalty also influence the purchase of fragrances/cosmetics. Therefore, these products can be advantageous for businesses seeking to attract repeat customers to their stores.

6. Conclusion

Based on the study findings, it is recommended that businesses prioritize the use of centralized application channels, as they align with consumer preferences for convenience and lower risks associated with product quality and financial transactions. The centralized approach allows for easier product returns or refunds, providing dissatisfied customers with the assurance of hassle-free resolution in case the received items do not meet their specifications.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript.

Statement of informed consent

In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

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